

DEVELOPMENT OF A 3D FINITE ELEMENT MODEL OF A QUASI-STATIC INDENTATION TEST IN A TYPE III CYLINDER

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes work performed to investigate the structural performance of a Type III pressure vessel. A 3D finite element model of a quasi-static indentation test was developed to predict metal-composite delamination under the indentation area as well as residual indentation depth. Further investigation of the metal-composite de-cohesion was performed through the development of an experimental analysis of a pseudo-2D quasi static indentation on a ring specimen obtained from a Type III pressure vessel. Results are discussed in relation to experimental data previously obtained and data generated through recent experiments. Limitations and improvements associated with different modelling parameters (e.g. boundary conditions) are discussed and considered for the future stages of the project.

1 INTRODUCTION

This project investigates the structural behaviour of composite pressure vessels under quasi-static indentation loading, which has been shown to be a useful proxy for impact. Composite pressure vessels are cylindrical containers designed to hold gases at high pressures (up to 700 Bar). They are available in different types: Type I, pure metal pressure vessel; Type II, metal cylinders with a composite wrapped hoop section; Type III, made of an aluminium liner fully wrapped in composite filaments and Type IV, made of a plastic liner fully wrapped in composite filaments. Due to their good strength-to-weight ratio, Type III and Type IV are attractive options to integrate within vehicles as part of their fuel system. These components are required to meet the same crash-worthiness regulations as the vehicle as a whole; this has hitherto been achieved largely by empirical approaches[1]. There is a need to develop analytical capability to improve the ability to predict performance and design Type III and IV cylinders for damage tolerance under impact loading, and subsequent cyclic fatigue.

There have been several studies regarding stress distribution and damage development within type III cylinders subjected to pressure and impact loads. For instance, Han *et al.* [2] proposed different techniques to model type III cylinders under pressure loading and validate them through experimental tests. In their study, they use 3D finite elements to model the stress distribution resulting from the loading case. Although their model showed acceptable results when compared to whole cylinder responses, the study focused on the stress distribution and damage occurring in the composite region of the pressure vessel, that is, no damage was assessed in the liner region. Subsequently, Son used this technique to develop a model for a Type III cylinder subject to a whole cylinder drop test[3], in which 3D elements, residual stresses resulting from autofrettage manufacturing process and friction between the liner and the composite layers were included. Son's model was used to evaluate the structural state of a cylinder after an impact based only on the "failure index" of the outermost layer. Despite good correlation with experimental tests, the study does not include information regarding the influence of the damage on the fatigue life of the cylinder. Sulaiman et al.[4] developed a finite element model of a type III cylinder to investigate how the fibre angle orientation affects overall performance. Prediction of burst pressure and

shell displacement was performed using the maximum stress as the failure criteria. Marzbanrad *et al.*[4] performed a similar study in which they evaluated the influence of the fibre angle orientation on the stress distribution and applied it to evaluate fatigue life. Their model lacks detail regarding liner damage, matrix failure and delamination areas.

The above studies focused on predicting damage modes such as delamination and matrix failure caused by pressure application or a low-velocity impact event. However, other damage mechanisms have been observed in type III cylinders that have not been studied deeply. Previous research based on experimental tests, concluded that a type III cylinder subjected to a quasi-static indentation test (a good proxy for a low-velocity impact) will develop a blister like failure, that is, a separation between the liner and the carbon fibre layers, with plastic deformation of the liner[5]. Moreover, it was shown that there is a direct correlation between the depth of the blister in the liner and the fatigue life of the cylinder, i.e. the deeper the blister the more the reduction on the fatigue cycle life.

The relation between the existence of the liner blister and the fatigue life performance reduction can be understood with the concepts of damage resistance and damage tolerance. The former refers to the capacity of a structure to withstand damage and the latter concerns the load carrying capability of a structure with the presence of pre-existing damage. If type III cylinders' damage tolerance can be properly assessed, better design approaches can be developed in order to ensure the integrity of the component throughout its service life. Hence, analysis of the blister formation mechanism (occurring at the aluminium-composite interface) is required.

In summary, this project aims to develop a 3D finite element model to predict the blister formation and separation between the aluminium liner and the composite layers of a type III cylinder. For this model, it is assumed that, as a result of the autofrettage process, there is a bond between the liner and the composite material whereas in previous research no bonding was considered. Consequently, de-cohesion progression is investigated in this model via the definition of the mechanical properties of the interface by applying cohesive zone modelling (CZM). In an initial approach, results were compared to data previously obtained in experimental tests to validate the model[5]. Furthermore, a pseudo-2D indentation test was performed on a ring specimen, extracted from a whole cylinder, to observe the de-cohesion progression using imaging techniques. Modelling of this experiment is the focus in the current work for direct experimental/numerical comparison.

2 METHODOLOGY

The project has been divided into two major activities: developing a full size cylinder to compare to previous experiments and to develop a pseudo-2D line indentation experiment to observe the metal-liner de-cohesion.

2.1 Full 3D cylinder indentation model

Previous indentation experiments were developed and presented in [5]. A full size 3D finite element model of a Type III cylinder was developed to replicate the response observed in the experiments, with a particular focus on the final residual depth. In the model, the indentation was performed in the cylindrical region of the pressure vessel with an 8 mm spherical indenter. The simulation was developed using *Abaqus*TM in two steps; a loading step to create the indentation and an unloading step to observe the residual deformation. The model assumes the composite wrap as a homogeneous material, hence no delamination fibre fracture has been captured, however this approximation was found to be sufficient at this stage of the model development.

In order to save computational time, 1/4th of the cylinder was modelled using appropriate boundary conditions. The dome region of the cylinder is known to be complex as the filament directions constantly vary over the surface as well as through thickness[2]. Moreover, the indentation is considered far from this region, thus, the dome geometry was not modelled to avoid the complexity involved. An end plate was included in the model, with a bending stiffness matched to that of the dome instead, to provide

appropriate boundary conditions. Two different cylinder sizes were used to create different models. The geometric characteristics of each cylinder are described in Table 1.

Table 1. Geometric dimensions of the Type III cylinder

Model	Water Volume [l]	Length [mm]	Outside Diameter [mm]	Liner Thickness [mm]	Carbon Fibre Thickness [mm]
A	1.0	295	85	1.8	2.0
B	6.8	525	159	2.2	4.3

The aluminium alloy used for the liner was a 6061-T6. Both plastic and elastic properties of the material are included in the model. The composite material is a carbon fibre reinforced polymer with a stacking sequence of $[\pm 55_2/0_4]_3$. Mechanical properties of the materials are described in Table 2.

Table 2. Material properties

Name	Young's Modulus [GPa]	Yield Strength [MPa]	Poisson's Ratio	Shear Modulus [GPa]
Aluminum	69	270	0.33	-
CFRP	$E_1 = 161.74$ $E_2 = E_3 = 9.5$	-	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.33$ $\nu_{23} = 0.43$	$G_{12} = G_{13} = 4.57$ $G_{23} = 3.1$

Figure 1 shows the final model of the cylinder. The indenter and the support are considered rigid, that is, they are assumed to have infinite stiffness and no deformation will be produced in these elements.

Figure 1. Full cylinder FE model; 1) liner, 2) Composite wrap, 3) Cohesive elements, 4) Support, 5) Steel plate, 6) indenter

The main component of the model are cohesive elements used to simulate the metal-composite interface. Cohesive zones are governed by a traction-separation law, which can be interpreted physically as defining a critical maximum stress and total energy for fracture (the area under the force-displacement curve) which is equal to the total critical strain energy release rate. A typical constitutive response for a traction-separation law is divided into damage initiation and damage evolution. The former occurs when the traction reaches a value at which damage starts and the latter describes the rate at which the stiffness of the cohesive zone is degraded[6]. Figure 2 shows a bilinear traction-separation law where σ_{max} is

the maximum traction, δ_{sep} is the displacement at separation and G_c is the critical energy release rate, which is the total energy dissipated as a result of the damage process[7]. The implementation of the cohesive zone in this project is via cohesive elements, which allow better control of the damage initiation and evolution parameters. Each of the parameters defining the cohesive element has been investigated with regard to their influence on the structural response after the quasi-static indentation.

Figure 2. Bilinear traction-separation law

2.2 Pseudo-2D line indentation

Further work has been performed to investigate the de-cohesion progression from an experimental perspective. A pseudo 2D-line experiment has been developed. The pseudo-2D line indentation refers to an indentation developed across the thickness of a ring-like specimen obtained by cutting a Type III cylinder into small slices (see Figure 3), ending with a component that resembles an aluminium ring wrapped in carbon fibre. The indentation experiment was complemented with Digital Image Correlation (DIC) techniques to obtain strain fields of the region of interest, which is the indentation area, and the volume including the resulting damage and blister formation.

Figure 3. Ring specimen geometry

The test was performed on a universal electromechanical test machine. A v-shaped support was used along with two 8-mm radius cylindrical pins to introduce the indentation into the cylinder (see Figure 4). One of the pins was placed on top of the other as a self-alignment method and hence produce a uniform load distribution across the specimen length. The support was placed on top of the specimen so that the indentation area would be relatively static during the whole experiment and, thus, it would reduce the noise during the image recording process from the DIC. The experiment involved observing the damage during the indentation loading and unloading, both developed at a load rate of 2 mm/min.

Figure 4. Pseudo 2D-line indentation set up

3 RESULTS

3.1 Full 3D cylinder indentation model

Different parameters were varied within the cohesive zone to investigate their influence on the overall response. To measure the accuracy of this model, force-displacement curves were obtained from the model and compared to those obtained in the experimental tests. Figure 5 shows the force-displacement curve of the FE model using different traction values compared to the experimental data under different traction values. Here, it can be observed that the initial stiffness remains constant among the three different configurations. However, the post-yielding behaviour shows some differences, especially with the highest interfacial strength value $\sigma_{II} = \sigma_{III} = 80$ MPa. The values of 30 MPa and 50 MPa showed similar acceptable correlation behaviour, although the latter displays a better unloading correlation to the experimental curve. However, the small difference in resultant behaviour shown by the 30 MPa and 50 MPa values suggest that these parameters can be modified with negligible influence on the final response, but adding the benefit of enlarging the cohesive zone length, increasing the smallest element size of the model and, as a consequence, reducing the computational time.

Figure 5. Force-displacement curve of Type III cylinder at different interfacial strengths (model A)

It was observed that varying the interface strength of the cohesive zone did not have significant influence on these results. However, when comparing the force-displacement curve for the bigger cylinder a major difference can be observed (see Figure 6). Despite a good correlation to the initial elastic response, the behaviour obtained using the geometry of model B did not match the change in slope of the curve, which is related to the aluminium yielding. Furthermore, the load-drop towards the end of the loading stage, related to delamination and fibre breakage, was not adequately captured by the model. Thus, even the overall response of the model is acceptable, damage on the composite wrap must be included to achieve a better force-displacement behaviour correlation.

Figure 6. Force-displacement curve of Type III cylinder (model B)

3.2 Pseudo-2D line indentation

A force-displacement curve was obtained from the pseudo-2D line indentation test and is presented in Figure 7. The curve exhibits an initial elastic response followed by small drops similar to those observed in the full cylinder curves. Images were processed at the beginning and at the end of the main load drops (A, B and C) using DIC, to investigate the damage mechanisms related to each of them. Figure 8 shows strain fields of the indentation area, in which is possible to observe delamination after load drops A and B respectively. Figure 9 shows the strain field of the indentation after load drop C, in which it is possible to observe metal-composite delamination. This progression of delamination suggests a strong bond between the liner and the carbon fibre, and the modification of this bonding could be critical to the residual indentation depth.

Figure 7. Force-displacement curve of ring specimen under pseudo-2D indentation

Figure 8. Delamination observed after load drops A and B

Figure 9. Metal-composite de-cohesion after load drop C

These results suggest that the progression of the damage occurring on both the liner and the composite after the indentation are important in defining the overall response. Prior to the metal-composite de-cohesion, delamination damage on the composite has been observed. Regarding the modelling, this observation leads to the conclusion that including composite damage in the model is critical to predict the de-cohesion and residual indentation depth. This experiment will be used as basis to develop a further stage of the modelling in which composite delamination is included in the model.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The project aims to develop a 3D FE model that predicts the characteristics of the de-cohesion observed after an indentation has been performed on a Type III cylinder. To achieve this, two major activities have been developed in the project: a full-size 3D FE model and an experimental pseudo-2D indentation to investigate the de-cohesion. From the full-size cylinder model it was concluded that the dome regions of the cylinder can be modelled using steel plates with similar stiffness to simplify the model and reduce the computational cost. However, it is suggested to perform a similar study on the full-sized cylinder adding more information to the model such as the damage mechanisms on the composite region. Furthermore, it was indicated that modifying the stiffness of the cohesive zone does not have a significant effect on the overall force-displacement behaviour of the cylinder. It is suggested that this characteristic of the model could be used to explore larger cohesive length sizes and reduce computational time.

In regard to the pseudo-2D indentation experimental procedure, it was concluded that despite the geometric and boundary condition differences, the response from the ring specimen corresponds (to a reasonable extent) to the experiments previously developed in [5]. Major delamination damage mechanisms were observed within the composite prior to aluminium-composite de-cohesion. This order of events suggests strong bonding between the two materials. This information will be used to feed the FE model in future steps.

5 FUTURE WORK

The current modelling and experimental activities are preliminary work which is part of a validated full-size 3D FE model. From the results presented here and the conclusions achieved future activities were defined:

1. Develop a 3D FE ring model under a pseudo-2D indentation. This model aims to combine metal-composite de-cohesion and delamination damage mechanisms. Use the experimental results to validate and calibrate adequate cohesive zone parameters.
2. Use the parameters from the validated ring model to develop a 3D full size cylinder which includes different damage mechanisms for a better force-displacement and residual indentation prediction. Validate the model against previous data.
3. Use the validated 3D full size cylinder to develop parametric investigation aiming for a reduction on the residual indentation depth.

REFERENCES

- [1] R.-M. Wang, S.-R. Zheng, and Y.-P. Zheng, 'Introduction to polymer matrix composites', *Polym. Matrix Compos. Technol.*, pp. 1–548, 2011.
- [2] M.-G. G. Han *et al.*, 'Evaluation of modeling techniques for a type III hydrogen pressure vessel (70 MPa) made of an aluminum liner and a thick carbon/epoxy composite for fuel cell vehicles', *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 37, no. 11, pp. 12771–12781, 2012.
- [3] M. G. Han and S. H. Chang, 'Evaluation of structural integrity of Type-III hydrogen pressure vessel under low-velocity car-to-car collision using finite element analysis', *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 148, pp. 198–206, 2016.
- [4] J. Marzbanrad, A. Paykani, A. Afkar, and M. Ghajar, 'Finite element analysis of composite high-pressure hydrogen storage vessels', *Environ. Sci.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 63–74, 2013.
- [5] T. M. Allen, 'Damage Development and Post-Impact Performance of Composite Overwrapped Pressure Vessels Subjected to Low Velocity Impact', University of Southampton, 2017.
- [6] Dassault Systemes, '32.5.6 Defining the constitutive response of cohesive elements using a traction-separation description', 2014.
- [7] A. Turon, P. P. Camanho, J. Costa, and J. Renart, 'Accurate simulation of delamination growth under mixed-mode loading using cohesive elements: Definition of interlaminar strengths and elastic stiffness', *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 92, no. 8, pp. 1857–1864, 2010.